

WHAT IS THE COLOR OF CHORO? COLOR PREFERENCES FOR AN INSTRUMENTAL BRAZILIAN POPULAR MUSIC GENRE

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ABSTRACT

This project explores how a synesthetic experience related to music perception and color association varies across cultures, and whether music with more energetic expressions elicits richer color responses. A total of 206 participants took part in a survey using a customized web page. The participants got to listen to excerpts of Brazilian music in the genre *Choro* and got to choose one or more color that matched the music the most. The music excerpts were chosen based on their portrayal of the emotions joy, tender and sorrow. The results showed differences in color preferences for each emotional expression studied across different groups. Furthermore, a correlation between the subjective intensity of the excerpt (considering that, in terms of intensity, Joy > Tender > Sorrow) and the variety of colors chosen by the participants was observed. In general the results supports previous research in this field with happiness or joy is often correlated to the color yellow and sorrow to the color blue. The excerpts that portrayed tenderness had most participants choosing the color yellow but also green for non-Brazilians. Due to the limits of the study, the results are not conclusive. More research is needed to get a better understanding of the impact of utilizing color combination rather than single colors to match music or emotional expressions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Color psychology is an underdeveloped area of research but there are findings that are consistent and give an insight into how the brain works [1]. One of these insights is a connection between color and emotions where a person can be affected emotionally by color and color can convey an emotion [1–3]. Studies have shown that people tend to follow certain patterns when associating emotions to colors which could be attributed to multiple factors like cultural coding and associations [1, 3].

Music is also connected to emotions according to findings that suggest that people generally create playlists based on moods [1].

Patterns are also present when associating music to colors, where brighter colors were matched with positive emotions and darker colors were matched with negative ones. This was then confirmed to correspond with music sounding sad due to being in a minor key and music sounding happy by being in a major key [4].

In a related study [2], that touches on connections between emotions and music, 22 participants matched musical excerpts with a colored circle. They used a joystick and a drawing tablet to choose the color and change the size of a circle based on what they were hearing. It was found that happy music was associated with the color yellow, angry music with large red circles and sad with small blue circles. This study also found that preferences for color had no significant effect on the results. A significant difference between genders was found when choosing the size of the circle but no other significant differences were found [2].

In another study [5] participants indicated their preferences in multiple online questionnaires for different visualization methods such as colors, icons, fonts and avatars. In the questionnaire about colors, participants listened to music from different genres including blues, classical, latin, jazz, and metal. They were presented with a color and asked to associate it to the best fitting one among three music genres. A majority of the participants were from Finland and some from various parts of Asia. The results showed major differences between participants from different cultures, with at the best 26–38% of the participants choosing the same color-genre association [5].

Studies of association between music and colors can lead to new possibilities of representing musical information in a visual, graphical, non-verbal way. This in turn can be used in the construction of engaging interfaces for composing and studying music, or exploring and managing musical collections and databases [5, 6].

The study presented in the next sections investigated the associations between certain songs and colors, and focused on the Brazilian instrumental genre *Choro*, also known as *Chorinho*. The possible differences in the choices made by Brazilian and non-Brazilian participants were of particular interest.

2. METHOD

An online interactive website was developed for this experiment, in which participants were asked to choose colors and color combinations matching a particular musical ex-

Country of origin	Male	Female	Non-binary
Brazil	43	116	1
Other	19	26	1
Total	62 (30%)	142 (69%)	2 (1%)

Table 1: Participants demographics.

cerpt. The color values that were represented on the website were the default colors on CSS when writing the name of the color (e.g color:red). Two versions of the website were created, one in English and one in Portuguese.

2.1 Participants

The website questionnaire was sent and shown to different people on campus of KTH Royal Institute of Technology as well as families in Brazil. The link to the experiment was spread around by the participants. A total of 206 people were recruited for the experiment, where 77.2% were from Brazil and 22.8% were from different countries such as Sweden, Germany, China, Spain, Croatia, Mexico, India and others. Their age varied from 7 to 76 years, with a median age of 43 and a mean of 43.8. Of all participants, 43.7% reported experience playing a musical instrument, and 12% reported experience creating music.

See Table 1 for the number of participants organized according to their country of origin and gender.

2.2 Stimuli

The authors of this study individually collected sets of different Choro tunes which could communicate different emotional expressions. After listening to the tunes, based on the author’s interpretation, it was decided that the emotions communicated by the music were joy, sorrow and tenderness. Out of the total number of excerpts, six excerpts of Choro songs that was communicating the strongest emotions were chosen, two for each of the three emotions (see Table 2).

2.3 Procedure

Participants were invited to participate in an online experiment. They were first asked to answer questions about their musical experience, age, gender and country of origin. After that, they were presented with an interface where they could listen to each of the six excerpts and select among eight colors (see Table 3) depending on how much they felt their selection matched the music. Multiple colors could be chosen for each music excerpt, and the background of the web page changed with the choices in a checkered pattern, allowing the participants to experiment freely with different colors or color combinations (see Figure 1). Participants could only submit their choice after a system validation that checked if at least one color was selected for each excerpt, and if the demographic information was complete.

Participants were not told that the study was related to emotions, and no mentions of emotions were ever made to them.

Figure 1: An example of the interface for color selection while listening to the excerpt. The participant could experiment and play with the color combination and the background would update to match the selection.

Figure 2: Percentage of users that chose a given color to a Joy excerpt (colors picked by less than 40% of the users are transparent to highlight the most picked colors.)

3. RESULTS

3.1 Overall results in color preferences according to country of origin

Normalized color preferences for each emotional expression (Joy, Sorrow, Tender) across the two groups Brazilians and non-Brazilians are summarized in Figures 2, 3 and 4.

Since it can be difficult to compare color preferences across groups by comparing the two sets of bars, we introduced a “preference difference” chart (see for example Figure 5). In this chart, for each color and each emotional expression, an arrow represents the preference difference between the two groups, presented in percentage points (pp). In this way, the chart highlights the relative differences in preferences across the two groups. We can notice, for example, that non-Brazilians showed more preference for orange in Joy excerpts than Brazilians. For these kinds of excerpts, Brazilians showed more preference than non-Brazilians for colors green and blue (see Figure 5).

For the Sorrow excerpts, non-Brazilians showed more preference for red and significantly more for blue than Brazil-

Name	Song time stamp	Composer	Emotion	Link to sound
Brasileirinho	0:00-0:32	Waldir Azevedo	Joy	link
Apanhei te cavaquinho	0:00-0:36	Ernesto Nazareth	Joy	link
Carinhoso	0:00-0:35	Pixinguinha & João De Barro	Tender	link
Gosto que me encosco	0:24-1:00	Sinhô	Tender	link
Flor do mal	0:00-0:39	Anacleto De Medeiros	Sorrow	link
Lamentos	0:00-0:33	Pixinguinha	Sorrow	link

Table 2: Chosen excerpts. The song time stamps column corresponds to where in the piece the selected excerpt comes from.

Color	H	S(%)	V(%)
magenta	300	100.0	100.0
pink	300	45.4	93.3
blue	240	100.0	100.0
cyan	180	100.0	100.0
green	120	100	39.2
yellow	60	100.0	100.0
orange	39	100.0	100.0
red	0	100.0	100.0

Table 3: The HSV values of each color chosen.

Figure 3: Percentage of users that chose a given color to a Tender excerpt (colors picked by less than 40% of the users are transparent to highlight the most picked colors.)

ians. On the other hand, Brazilians picked more yellow than non-Brazilians for this emotion.

Finally, for the Tender excerpts, the most important difference was in the choice of orange, for which non-Brazilians showed much more preference.

We applied the same visualization method when comparing groups of other features such as age or gender.

3.2 Gender

In this comparison, regarding the Joy excerpts, women showed more preference for orange than men, while men showed more preference for magenta (see Figure 6).

For the Sorrow excerpts, men showed more relative pref-

Figure 4: Percentage of users that chose a given color to a Sorrow excerpt (colors picked by less than 40% of the users are transparent to highlight the most picked colors.)

Figure 5: Differences in color association for different emotions between Brazilian and non-Brazilians. Arrows indicate preference difference in percentage points. Differences below 15pp are transparent. Left pointing arrows: non-Brazilians. Right pointing arrows: Brazilians.

erence for violet, while women showed for magenta.

The most relevant difference lies in the Tender excerpts, where women strongly showed more preference for cyan than men, and men showed more preference for red.

3.3 Gender differences between country of origin

The color choices for male and female Brazilian users looks similar with the exception of magenta being chosen less by males compared to females. For sorrow, no color was chosen 40% of the time or more but blue and pink for females were chosen slightly below 40% of the time. For tender, yellow, pink and red was chosen more by females than males where the yellow was chosen almost by 50% of the female compared to the males below 40%. The cyan

Figure 6: Differences in color association for different emotions between genders. Arrows indicate preference difference in percentage points. Differences below 10pp are transparent. Left arrows: Females. Right arrows: Males.)

Figure 7: Percentage of Brazilian users that chose a given color, divided into male and female

was chosen by more than 40% of the males and below 30% of the females (see Figure 7).

For the group with non-Brazilians, the color yellow and orange was chosen by more than 20% of the males when listening to excerpts that represented joy and tenderness. Cyan was chosen by more than 20% of the male participants and less than 5% by the female participants for tender excerpts. For sorrow excerpts, blue was the most common color for both groups (see Figure 8).

3.4 Experience playing an instrument

The group of participants who declared to play or have played an instrument showed a greater preference for the use of orange in Joy excerpts and for violet in Sorrow excerpts (see Figure 9).

3.5 Age

When comparing across the groups of participants under the age of 43 years (the median age of our sample) and over 43, the most remarkable fact is a relevant difference between the groups' preferences for yellow in all emotions (see Figure 10). People older than 43 years chose yellow 20% more often for excerpts that convey Sorrow, than younger people. On the other hand, people below 43 years of age preferred to associate the color yellow to the excerpts that conveyed Tenderness and Joy.

Figure 8: Percentage of non-Brazilian users that chose a given color, divided into male and female

Figure 9: Differences in color association for different emotions between participants with and without experience playing an instrument. Arrows indicate preference difference in percentage points. Differences below 10pp are transparent. Left arrows: Participants with music experience. Right arrows: Participants without music experience.

Figure 10: Differences in color association for different emotions between participants under 43 and over 43 years old. Arrows indicate preference difference in percentage points. Differences below 10pp are transparent.

3.6 Relationship between the number of colors chosen and the liveliness of the excerpt

Regardless of the country of origin, on average, participants tended to choose a greater number of distinct colors the more energetic the excerpts were (see Figure 11).

4. DISCUSSION

Overall, the results somewhat followed previous findings regarding the association of hues to emotions [2, 4], albeit with differences: in our study, preference for red surpassed yellow in Joy excerpts, and preferences for blue surpassed violet in Sorrow excerpts. For Tender excerpts, yellow was overall the most chosen color (see Figure 12).

These differences may reflect some of the limitations of our study, namely the limited set of colors from which participants could select their preferences, and the classification of the excerpts in the three different emotions, which was based solely on our perception and experience in mu-

Figure 11: Average number of different colors chosen by all participants for each excerpt.

Figure 12: General color preferences for excerpts of each emotion (percentage of all participants that chose the color for at least one of the excerpts of a given emotion).

sis performance and research. It would have been interesting to collect user ratings of the excerpts in terms of emotions.

However, these limitations made the survey simpler and quicker to answer, and that may be part of the reason for the large number of participants, alongside the playful character of the interface. Several participants reported that they “had fun” taking part in the experiment, and felt spontaneously compelled to share the survey with friends, and continued playing with the interface beyond the experiment. To assess the consistency of the excerpts’ associations into emotions, we can compare the number of times each color was chosen for each excerpt of the same emotion (see Figure 13).

As mentioned above, the classification of the music excerpts into three emotions was made by the authors of this study, and could be considered as indicative labels for the

Figure 13: Comparative color preferences for each emotion’s pair of excerpts.

expression communicated by the six excerpts. For a future study, we could perform a listening test in which participants are asked to rate the perceived communicated emotion of each musical excerpt.

Our definition of the represented emotions could be different from what others would perceive it as, especially tenderness. The results could be suggesting to that the emotion that corresponds to tenderness in this case could be an emotion that is between a spectrum of joy and sorrow, as the amount of people choosing yellow and orange is similar for both joy and tender, but the amount of red, green and magenta is lower in tender compared to joy. The amount of people choosing cyan and pink for tender are more similar to the results of sorrow.

4.1 An indication of the role of shared cultural references in color preferences

A limitation of our study was the fact that the chosen genre and some of the excerpts were probably well-known among the majority of the participants. This may have an effect on the music-color associations because of past personal experiences related with the excerpts. This may hinder the generalization of the results in this study.

On the other hand, for a group of people from the same culture, or with common experiences, the associations might arise from shared cultural references, and those could possibly be generalized for particular groups. With that in mind, one difference in color preference comparisons across groups that caught our attention was the greater presence of green for Joy among Brazilian participants (see Figure 14).

It is relevant to mention that one of the excerpts chosen for Joy came from one of the most beloved Brazilian songs, “Brasileirinho” (transl.: “little Brazilian”). Our hypothe-

Figure 14: Percentage of users that chose green and yellow together for the Joy excerpts.

sis is that color preferences among Brazilians for this song might reflect the association of this song with their country and their national colors (the colours of the Brazilian flag are green and yellow). Since participants could pick more than one color for each excerpt, we investigated the number of green-yellow combinations for the two Joy excerpts.

Figure 14 shows that there was no big difference between the frequency that the green-yellow combination was chosen by Brazilians or non-Brazilians for the other Joy excerpt (“Apanhei-te Cavaquinho”). On the other hand, this combination was much more frequent among Brazilians for “Brasileirinho”, when compared with non-Brazilians. It was also twice as frequent among Brazilians for “Brasileirinho” than for “Apanhei-te Cavaquinho”.

Figure 15: Differences (percentage points) in preferences for the color yellow between all participants under (Left arrows) and over 43 years of age (Right arrows).

4.2 Age and preference for yellow

According to our results (see Figure 15) there is a difference in choosing the color yellow for different emotions depending on participant age. This could be due to cultural reasons that people who are older than 43 associate yellow more to sorrow than younger people. It could be due to yellow and green possibly being chosen together, and green is sometimes associated to sickness or calmness which would be more appropriate for the characteristics of sorrow.

Another reason could be general experimentation from the users. Participants being able to select multiple colors forming the screen background rather than selecting only one isolated color, opens up for different combinations, and this has rarely been explored in previous research on color associations to music.

Tender for both male Brazilians and non-Brazilians has similar proportions of the percentages of chosen colors which

could suggest that some sort of commonality exists, but for the female participants there is limited similarities.

4.3 Number of colors chosen according to the liveliness of the excerpt

As mentioned above, we noticed that participants chose a greater number of different colors, on average, for the more energetic excerpts. This can be seen in the visualization presented in Figure 16, in which each little square represents the color chosen for a particular excerpt by each of the 206 participants. This could be researched further to gain an understanding on emotion and color association.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, we observed that the same excerpts taken from a particular regional musical genre seem to elicit different color associations from people of that region compared with people from other regions. The results also suggests a correlation between the number of different colors chosen by the participants and the subjective energy, liveliness of the excerpt.

Having a large number of participants in a study such as this opens fascinating possibilities of groupings and comparison across groups, to study and understand how cultural context and experience might influence music-color association. It could be of great interest to do similar types of studies with color combinations to get more data about this subject as this study’s results are not conclusive. This is because the limitations of this study opens up for uncertainty for multiple factors that could affect the results, such as prior experience with the genre, color associations for different cultures and the representations of colors shown. The difference between the groups “Brazilians” and “non-Brazilians” are unbalanced as one groups is significantly bigger than the other and therefore could create a skewed result where the outliers have a bigger effect on the results.

A better understanding of these relationships may be relevant for the development of more customized experiences and interfaces in future applications such as music players, computer games, or metaverse applications. The engagement of participants with the application presented in this study indicates that it was (and is) worth developing a customized interface that makes participants interact with the survey in a fun, lighthearted way.

Finally, the rich data collected in this study offers many interesting possibilities for visualizations in the future. All data and code used in the analysis and preparation of all the charts presented in this report, as well as the code used for the development of the survey’s custom interface is available on the following repository: <https://github.com/tiago-kth/human-perception>

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Figure 16: Representations of the individual colors chosen by all users for each excerpt.

This study has been peer reviewed and feedback has been implemented, such as fixing layout and typos. Parts of the method has been explained further where confusion occurred and the exploratory nature of the study has been emphasized.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Voong and R. Beale, “Music organisation using colour synaesthesia,” in *CHI’07 extended abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 2007*, pp. 1869–1874.
- [2] P. Lindborg and A. K. Friberg, “Colour association with music is mediated by emotion: Evidence from an experiment using a cie lab interface and interviews,” *PloS one*, vol. 10, no. 12, p. e0144013, 2015.
- [3] M. Zentner, “Preferences for colors and color—emotion combinations in early childhood,” *Developmental Science*, vol. 4, 11 2001.
- [4] R. Bresin, “What is the color of that music performance?” in *ICMC, 2005*.
- [5] J. Holm and H. Siirtola, “A comparison of methods for visualizing musical genres,” in *2012 16th International Conference on Information Visualisation*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 636–645.
- [6] M. Poast, “Color music: Visual color notation for musical expression,” *Leonardo*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 215–221, 2000.